

Jamboard as an Interactive Platform Toward Improving Students' Writing Competency in Stylistics and Discourse Analysis

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Abstract:- Writing skill is one of the macro skills that is considered as the most difficult skill to develop which requires an appropriate pedagogy, instruction, setting and platform. As the contemporary technologies emerge, the educational setting and platform have also been influenced thus technology-mediated instructions and teaching also emerge. So much so, there are some technology-mediated instructions and platforms that need to be evaluated in terms of its effectiveness in honing, enhancing and developing the skill and competency of the learners. With all these in mind, the researchers aimed to evaluate and determine the effectiveness of technology-mediated instruction like Jamboard as an interactive platform in improving the writing competency of the English major students in Stylistics and Discourse Analysis. The researchers employed quasi-experimental method in which the respondents are grouped as treatment group and controlled group. With a p-value of 0.000, t-value of 5.940 and mean difference of 8.4000, the research study revealed that there is a statistically significant difference in the posttest scores between treatment and controlled group. Therefore, the researchers concluded that the null hypothesis is rejected which means that the intervention is effective toward improving the writing competency of the respondents. The researchers strongly recommend further study using a mixed-method relative to Jamboard as an interactive platform toward students' writing competency in order to broaden the scope of knowledge, understanding and findings based on the narratives and experiences of the respondents.

Keywords:- Jamboard, Quasi-experimental, Significant difference, Stylistics and Discourse Analysis, Writing Skill.

I. INTRODUCTION

English is the most widely used language and recognized as a Lingua Franca. As the world becomes more integrated into a global society reliant on contemporary technologies, the necessity to communicate in English both in speaking and writing has become increasingly evident. Furthermore, the world is encountering rampant changes and development in the present time. Innovations, in a wink of an eye, emerged and provided opportunities in reinforcing the quality and status of education. In this

regard, innovations made a way to the emergence of new teaching methods toward the development, improvement and advancement of the learners (Oluyinka&Daenos, 2019) (10). In this way, innovation is progressively being utilized in classrooms to assist educators in achieving numerous pedagogical and instructive goals (Sprengrer & Schwaninger, 2021) (17).

According to Oluyinka & Daenos (2019), technology is viewed as an excellent aspect and ingredient toward providing students the opportunities to learn by means of being and serving as the mainstream of online learning. In addition, with the rapid increment of innovations, learning institutions were provided with the chances to utilize the internet as the main source of interaction and communication. In this regard, technology-based learning is making institutions more efficient and productive (10). Further, Okoye, Tort, Escamilla & Hosseini (2021) emphasized that technology-mediated education has become an essential part of modern teaching and learning instruction. Also, the internet has offered an ease of use to the educators and learners through the unlimited access to applications and software which can expedite teaching and learning (9).

As a matter of fact, Chan (2020) reinforced that there are applications and tools such as Google Jamboard which enable students to actively engage, participate and collaborate in the discussion (3). Jamboard is a Google service or tool which allows users to utilize text, photos, shapes, and drawings to creatively organize and present information (Petrov, 2021) (11). Furthermore, by allowing students to visually depict their learning and ideas, Jamboard helps improve classroom involvement. This also allows teachers to gather real-time insight into what their students understand. It is a great tool for in-person, online, synchronous, and asynchronous collaboration. More so, using digital whiteboard offers a variety of learning modes, including kinesthetic, visual, and auditory, verbal-social, visual-auditory, active, and active-verbal (Glover, Miller, Averis& Door, 2005 in Sjönvall, 2015) (5) (16). As a result, technology-mediated instruction and learning allowed people or learners to utilize technology beneficial to the acquisition of knowledge and skills. Sioco and De Vera (2018, p.1) mentioned that:

Adjacent to the person's ability to utilize technology successfully, it has become necessary to refine one's ability to speak or write effectively in English if one wants to participate in global trade, especially as English is extensively used in business and education (15).

Despite the numerous studies and authors that supported technology as a great tool in teaching through its platforms such as digital whiteboards, there are still few and limited recent studies that explore the technology-mediated instruction or platform that focused on its effectiveness in the writing competency of the learners.

For as much as language, particularly English, is concerned, it comprises of basic skills which can be referred to as macro skill. These include listening, speaking, reading and writing. Listening and speaking, among all the abilities, may be rated to be developed via critical analysis. As a result, these skills might also be referred to as instinctive skills. Reading and writing, on the other hand, are abilities that should be mastered in a specific environment. As a result, these might be classified as productive abilities. These are the abilities that can and should be learned in the most particular and familiar setting possible for students.

According to Gepila (2014), these macro skills are arranged in hierarchical manner and according to its hierarchy, writing is the last. The writing, as a macro skill, is the achievement of a certain level of skill in studying and mastering a language. A language learner is considered proficient if he or she can write in a language while following and practicing the limited rules of the language. So much so, writing is the most difficult skill to teach and develop when compared to other abilities. It must be taught and learned in the most appropriate setting (6).

In the study of Sioco & De Vera (2018), it has been found out that Filipinos scored a total mean of 6.69 in terms of the macro skills in English which comprises of reading, speaking, listening and writing. Hence, in the international context and standards, this result signified a low profile in the macro skills of the Filipinos (15).

Meanwhile, Sugumlu (2020) reiterated that writing skills, unlike listening and speaking abilities, which occur naturally in the natural world, may be taught officially through an appropriate educational setting (18). In a nutshell, the instructions and methods in teaching writing should be designed properly. One of the major approaches in teaching writing is the controlled writing activities. In this particular approach, it involves the processes such as prewriting, writing and post writing (Nunan, 2009 in Gepila, 2014) (8) (6).

Much as writing is a major consideration in the macro skills and in the development of the competency of a person in terms of language, writing can be defined as the narration of experiences and exercises that is grounded and based on the thoughts, ideas and feelings of every individual who has the ability to think and discern a certain issue or subject while following the rules and laws in grammar (Sugumlu, 2020) (18). Similarly, Al-Atabi (2020)

articulated that writing is the process of communicating thoughts and ideas in a legible manner by means of employing rules, written symbols and punctuations. In addition, writing can be a medium or platform for human communication which includes symbols as the representation of the language (1).

Writing skills comprise of three important components namely grammatical skill, compositional skill and domain knowledge. Baker (2011) explained the three components of writing skills: (1) Grammatical skill is the ability to construct sentences in a meaningful way with the aid of rules, laws and standards relative to structures of language. Specifically, this skill covers the proper usage of tenses, subject-verb agreement, word class appropriation, functions, cases, articles, conjunctions and prepositions; (2) Compositional skills is the ability to organize and construct words, phrases and sentences in order to produce an effect, to achieve cohesion and unity of ideas and thoughts in a composition. This skill involves the spelling, punctuations, paragraphing and sentence construction; and (3) Domain knowledge is a component of a writing skills that deals with the knowledge, analysis, understanding and interpretation of a writer toward a particular subject matter (2).

According to Rao and Durga (2018), writing is a challenging cognitive activity in which the writer must demonstrate simultaneous control of several aspects. Students who excel in writing may have a higher chance of succeeding. Writing is also used to communicate precise and succinct thoughts, ideas, and facts. Effective writing is a skill that students must develop for academic and professional success. Even more so, without writing, language is inadequate. To accomplish their academic and work requirements, all students require excellent writing skills (12).

Meanwhile, as the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) envisions quality and holistically developed Filipino learners despite the conundrums facing in the pandemic, Don Honorio Ventura State University (DHVSU) as a learning institution, is continuously catering students and providing them quality education. Specifically, the College of Education as the Center of Development in Teacher Education, also coincides with the aim of producing competent professionals. In line with this, English instructors are maximizing the power of technology to deliver comprehensive and quality discussions. However, English major students, whose prerequisites are language courses such as Stylistics and Discourse Analysis, are still experiencing challenges in terms of writing. This has been found out during the pre-assessment or diagnostic activity of the learners in the said course in which the stylistics teacher asked the students to create a sentence on how the learners will show and deliver their admiration toward someone in a creative manner or with their own styles. Unfortunately, only few students created sentences in the digital whiteboard even if there is an ease of access or use in the said platform.

Considering all these, the researchers conceptualized this action research study in order to address the problem concerning the writing competency of the learners in the online distance education. Hence, the researchers aimed to evaluate and describe the effectiveness of digital whiteboard such as Jamboard in improving the writing competency of the English major students in the course Stylistics and Discourse Analysis.

II. PROPOSED INNOVATION, INTERVENTION AND STRATEGY

A. Jamboard

Teaching and learning during the pandemic have slung everybody in education into a brand-new world of technology-based pedagogy. Digital whiteboards give students, at all capability levels, the potential chance to show their arrangement, to conduct interactive activities, to guard their responses, and to pay attention to their companions. As such, Jamboard is a digital whiteboard that allows learners to team up continuously utilizing either the Jamboard gadget or internet browser or mobile app (Epstein, 2021).

Moreover, Nagamani (2021) accentuated that Jamboard delivers real learning opportunities for both instructors and students. Students obtain a great deal of knowledge by participating in Jamboard activities, which promote communication and information literacy skills that are vital in the twenty-first century (7).

The figure 1 shows the digital whiteboard most specifically the Google Jamboard. The Google Jamboard was utilized as an interactive platform toward honing and improving the writing competency of the English major students particularly in the course Stylistic and Discourse Analysis.

Hence, the Google Jamboard as an interactive platform toward students' writing competency in Stylistic and Discourse Analysis was implemented with the use of following steps:

- Step 1: Conduct an output-based pretest (one-page analysis paper)
- Step 2: Group the respondents into two (Treatment and Controlled Group)
- Step 3: Discuss the topic about Stylistic Devices
- Step 4: Collate excerpts from a classic Filipino Short Story
- Step 5: Orient Treatment Group about the interactive activity in Jamboard
- Step 6: Actual activity in Jamboard (Treatment Group)
- Step 7: Create an analysis with 3-5 sentences applying the stylistic devices tackled and learned
- Step 8: Conduct output-based posttest (one-page analysis paper) to the students
- Step 9: Assess the effectiveness of the Google Jamboard to the writing competency by looking into the significant difference of the mean scores of Treatment and Controlled Group.

Fig. 1: Jamboard

The Google Jamboard as an interactive platform is an intervention that allows students to interact virtually while enhancing their writing competency as respondents exercise their skills by means of analyzing an excerpt from a classic Filipino short story with the aid and consideration of the stylistics devices. Virto and Lopez (2020) reiterated that Google Jamboard as an interactive smartboard that allows teachers and students to engage on a virtual whiteboard, allowing them to brainstorm ideas and create sketches (19).

Based on the intervention, it can be considered that the Google Jamboard is an interactive platform in improving and enhancing the writing competency of the learners most especially in Stylistics and Discourse Analysis.

III. ACTION RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This study was conducted to evaluate and determine the effectiveness of technology-mediated instruction like Jamboard as an interactive platform in improving the writing competency of the English major students in Stylistics and Discourse Analysis.

Hence, the following questions were utilized in the conduct of the study:

- What are the levels of writing competency of the respondents during the pretest in Stylistics and Discourse Analysis in terms of grammatical, compositional and domain knowledge?
- What are the levels of writing competency of the respondents in the posttest in Stylistics and Discourse Analysis in terms of grammatical, compositional and domain knowledge?
- Is there a significant difference between the posttest scores of the respondents in Controlled and Treatment group?
- Based on the findings of the study, what are the implications that can be deduced in improving the writing competency in Stylistics and Discourse Analysis?

Ho1: There is no significant difference between the pretest scores of the respondents in Controlled and Treatment group in Stylistics and Discourse Analysis.

Ho2: There is no significant difference between the posttest scores of the respondents in Controlled and Treatment group in Stylistics and Discourse Analysis.

IV. ACTION RESEARCH METHODS

A. Participants and/or other Sources of Data and Information

The researchers employed convenience sampling in gathering and determining the respondents of the study. According to Roman et. al. 2020, the convenience sampling technique is a nonprobability sampling technique which can be used in selecting respondents out of the total population which merely considers several factors like geographical proximity, accessibility, availability, and willingness (14).

Furthermore, researchers with time restrictions frequently selected convenience sampling since it takes less time to collect data and consults fewer standards than other sampling strategies.

Meanwhile, the respondents of the study are the 3rd year BSED English major students of the College of Education, Don Honorio Ventura State University. The table 1 shows the respondents under the controlled group and treatment group. It also presents the number of respondents who took the output-based pretest and posttest.

Strands	No. of Respondents	
	Pretest	Posttest
BSED English 3C (Control Group)	5	5
BSED English 3A (Treatment Group)	5	5
TOTAL	10 Respondents	

Table 1: Participants Of The Study

The researchers also utilized quantitative-descriptive method since the objectives of the researchers are to determine the raw and mean scores of the Treatment and Controlled Group both in the pretest and posttest, before and after the intervention, as well as the significant difference between the mean scores in the pretest and posttest of both groups.

The Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSEd) English 3A constituted the Jamboard. On the other hand, the Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSEd) English 3C constituted mere online lecture. Both groups came from the same department, degree program, and major or specialization.

Based on the results in the significant difference of the pretest scores of the groups, it has been found out that there is no significant difference with their scores in pretest. Hence, the categorization of the respondents per group was based on the section since there is no significant difference in their writing skills and competency in the pretest.

B. Data Gathering Methods

The study was centered on the difference between the online lecture and Jamboard. The conduct of this action research study utilized quasi-experimental research method or design in which the respondents are investigated as Treatment and Controlled Group. According to Rogers and Rovesz (2019), a quasi-experimental design looks for the causal relationship of the variables between independent and dependent variables. The independent variable is the variable that influences whereas the dependent variables is the variable being influenced. In other words, the independent variable is expected to influence the dependent variable in some way (13).

Moreover, the researchers determined two groups which are the treatment and controlled group. The controlled group used the online lecture method while the intervention or treatment group used the Jamboard as an interactive platform.

The researchers crafted and wrote a letter to conduct the study as well as the letter of consent that was given to the respondents. The researchers also sought the assistance and expertise of a stylistic teacher in validating the rubrics rating, interpretation and classic Filipino short stories that were used in the analysis of data as well as the checking of the analysis papers of the respondents. The pretest and posttest of the respondents were output-based in which the respondents from both groups created and crafted a one-page analysis paper. Furthermore, the researchers conducted the pretest after the two-week observation. Then, the researchers conducted the intervention to the treatment group for eight (8) weeks or equivalent to two (2) months. After the intervention, the researchers administered the posttest to the two groups. As the researchers collated and consolidated the analysis papers, the outputs were forwarded and given to the stylistic teacher in order to check and obtain the scores. Lastly, the scores were subjected to the computation and statistical treatment with the help of the statistician.

The results of the pretest and posttest were compared and the significant difference of the posttest scores between the two groups was determined, interpreted and analyzed. Based on the findings, implications were deduced and action plan was developed in order to improve and hone the writing competency of the English majors particularly in the Stylistics and Discourse Analysis course or subject.

Hence, the conduct of the research study is presented in a conceptual schema or framework. The said framework is reflected below.

Fig. 2: Paradigm of the Study

C. Data Analysis Plan

The researchers crafted a rubric that was utilized in checking the analysis papers of the respondents. The rubric comprises of the criteria that targets the three components of writing skills namely grammatical, compositional and domain knowledge. Moreover, the rubric also has its indicators and descriptions as well as the scale or scoring that ranges from 10 as the highest and 2 as the lowest. All in all, the highest score that can be obtained by the respondents is 30 and the lowest score is 8.

In analyzing and interpreting the data gathered, the researchers utilized descriptive and inferential statistics. The descriptive statistics are the average and overall scores. Meanwhile, for the inferential statistics, the researchers employed T-Test and Probability Value in order to

determine the significant difference of mean scores in the posttest between the treatment and controlled group.

For the Decision Criteria, if the computed P-Value is less than or equal to .05, the null hypotheses will be rejected. Much as if the computed P-Value is greater than .05, the null hypothesis will be accepted.

So much so, for the descriptive rating and interpretation of the level of writing competency of the respondents from both groups, a scale will be utilized. The scale is reflected below.

Lastly, the researchers utilize a scale in interpreting and describing the level of writing competency of the respondents. The scale is reflected below.

Verbal Interpretation for the Level of Writing Competency	Per Component (10)	Overall (30)
Excellent (E)	9-10	25-30
Good (G)	7-8	19-24
Average (A)	5-6	13-18
Fair (F)	3-4	7-12
Poor (P)	1-2	1-6

Table 2: Level Of Writing Competency Scale

V. RESULTS, DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION, RECOMMENDATION AND REFLECTION

This section presents the results, implications, conclusion, recommendation and reflection. The data presented in this section follows the arrangement of problems as illustrated in the Action Research Questions. Moreover, the data gathered from the respondents in both pretest and posttest were discussed, evaluated and analyzed.

A. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

LEVEL OF WRITING COMPETENCY (PRETEST)									
Group	Grammatical	V.I.	Compositional	V.I.	Domain Knowledge	V.I.	Overall	SD	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
Treatment	6.4	A	6	A	6	A	18.4	2.19089	AVERAGE (A)
Controlled	6	A	6.4	A	5.2	A	17.6	1.67332	AVERAGE (A)

Table 3: Level Of Writing Competency Of The Respondents In Pretest

Presented in the table 3 is the level of writing competency of the respondents in the pretest. As reflected in the table, the treatment group has an average score of 6.4 for grammatical, 6 for compositional and 6 for domain knowledge. All of the average scores of treatment group in terms of the components of writing competency are interpreted as Average.

Moreover, in terms of the pretest scores of the controlled group, the table indicates that controlled group has an average score of 6 for grammatical, 6.4 for composition and 5.2 for domain knowledge. Looking into these pretest scores, these average scores are all interpreted as Average as far as level of writing competency is concerned.

The table also presents the overall score and standard deviation values of the treatment and controlled groups in the pretest. As shown in the table, the Treatment group has an overall score of 18.4000 (sd=2.19089) in the pretest while the Controlled group has a mean of 17.6000 (sd=1.67332).

All in all, the level of writing competency of treatment group in the pretest is interpreted as average whereas the level of writing competency of the controlled group is also interpreted as average. This means that the level of writing competency of both groups is the same based on their pretest scores.

	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Pretest	.649	8	.535	.80000	-2.04303	3.64303

Table 4: Independent Sample T-Test Of Difference In Pretest

The table 4 presents the significant difference of the groups in terms of the pretest scores in stylistics and discourse analysis. With a t-value of 0.649 and mean difference of .8000, these values mean and imply that there is no significant different between the pretest scores of the respondents from both groups in Stylistics and Discourse Analysis. To further support this claim, the probability

value of the data reflected in the table is 0.535 which means it exceeds to the recommended value of 0.05 in order to reject the null hypothesis. This means that the first null hypothesis is supported. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the level of writing competency of the respondents from both groups in terms of their pretests scores in Stylistics and Discourse Analysis.

LEVEL OF WRITING COMPETENCY (POSTTEST)									
Group	Grammatical	V.I.	Compositional	V.I.	Domain Knowledge	V.I.	Overall	SD	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
Treatment	8.8	G	9.6	E	9.2	E	27.6	2.60768	EXCELLENT
Controlled	6	A	6.4	A	6.8	A	19.2	1.78885	GOOD

Table 5: Level Of Writing Competency Of The Respondents In Posttest

Presented in the table 5 is the level of writing competency of the respondents from both groups based on their posttest scores in Stylistics and Discourse Analysis. As shown in the table, the treatment group has an average score of 8.8 for grammatical interpreted as Good, 9.6 for compositional interpreted as Excellent and 9.2 for domain knowledge interpreted as Excellent. Meanwhile, for the controlled group, the group has an average score of 6 in grammatical, 6.4 in compositional and 6.8 for domain knowledge. These values or scores fall under the rating of Average. Moreover, the table indicates that the treatment group has an overall score of 27.6000 (sd=2.60768) interpreted as Excellent while the Controlled group has an overall score of 19.2000 (sd= 1.78885) interpreted as Average.

Looking into the average scores, the data revealed that there is an increase in the scores of both groups after the conducted method which are reflected in the posttest results. However, the data explicitly revealed that there is a huge increase in the posttest scores of the treatment group after the respondents undergone the Jamboard method or technique/strategy, compared to the Controlled group whose respondents undergone the online lecture method.

To further explain and understand the data situated in the table 5, the data also reveal the comparison and difference between the components of level of competency of the respondents from both groups. This shows that the level of competency of the treatment group in terms of grammatical, compositional and domain knowledge is higher than that of the controlled group.

	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Posttest	5.940	8	.000	8.40000	5.13882	11.66118

Table 6: Independent Sample T-Test Of Difference In Posttest

The table 6 presents the significant difference of the groups in terms of the posttest scores in Stylistics and Discourse Analysis. With a t-value of 5.940 and mean difference of 8.4000, the data reveal that there is a statistically significant difference in the posttest scores of the respondents from treatment and controlled group. To further support this finding, the probability value reflected in the table is 0.000 which means that there is indeed a significant difference in the posttest scores of the both groups in Stylistics and Discourse Analysis. Therefore, the

research study reveals that the second null hypothesis is rejected.

If to assess, the results show that the intervention conducted by the researchers to the treatment group has helped the respondents in improving their writing competency in Stylistics and Discourse Analysis. In addition, the Jamboard as an interactive platform toward students' writing competency has been found out effective.

	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Pretest	.649	8	.535	.80000	-2.04303	3.64303
Posttest	5.940	8	.000	8.40000	5.13882	11.66118

Table 7: Results Of Independent Sample T-Test Of Difference In Pretest And Posttest

Presented in the table 7 is the independent sample t-test of difference in the pretest and posttest of both groups in Stylistics and Discourse Analysis. As reflected in the table, the t-value in the pretest is .649 while on the posttest is 5.940. Looking into these values, it shows that there is a huge gap and difference between the t-values of respondents in terms of pretest and posttest scores.

Moreover, in terms of mean difference, the mean difference in the pretest scores is .80000 while in the posttest scores is 8.4000. If to assess, this finding coincided to the result in t-value which shows the difference between the scores in pretest and posttest. Hence, the data strengthen how the intervention conducted by the researchers became effective to the level of the writing competency of the learners especially to the intervention or treatment group.

- a) Implications deduced in the findings of the study
Jamboard as one of the learning platforms offered and invented by Google Services, has provided a lot of learning opportunities toward the students especially that the students are still in the online distance education. Moreover, Google Jamboard as an intervention, method and strategy, was utilized by the researchers in order to determine and evaluate its effectiveness toward the writing competency of the respondents of treatment group.

The findings of the present study implicate that the Jamboard, as an interactive platform, is an effective method in the development of the writing competency of the respondents under intervention or treatment group. Even though there is also a little increase in the mean score of controlled group after the online lecture method still, there is a huge gap or difference between the respondents who utilized Jamboard. This can be proven and supported with the t-value, p-value and mean difference reflected on the results of inferential statistics.

B. CONCLUSION

As writing is regarded to be the last skill in the hierarchy of macro skills and considered as the most difficult skill to develop, it must be taught, learned and

develop in a most effective, appropriate, conducive and essential setting and platform. In congruence with this, the researchers employed Google Jamboard as an interactive platform toward students' writing competency in Stylistics and Discourse Analysis.

Based on the results and findings of the study, the researchers concluded that the intervention employed has a significant effect toward the writing competency of the students especially the respondents under treatment group. More specifically, the researchers concluded that the Jamboard as an interactive platform toward students' writing competency is effective for it has been reflected in the t-value and mean score of the results that there is a difference between the posttest scores of treatment group and controlled group.

Meanwhile, given the probability value of 0.535, the first null hypothesis is supported which imply that there is no significant difference in the pretests scores between the groups in Stylistics and Discourse Analysis. Whereas, with the probability value of 0.000, it is therefore concluded that the second null hypothesis is rejected for the study revealed that there is significant difference in the posttests scores between the students in Controlled and Treatment group.

C. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results, implications and conclusion of the research study, the following are hereby recommended:

- The researchers strongly recommended that students should continuously utilize Google Jamboard as an interactive platform toward their writing competency. This platform is proven effective based from the findings of this research as reflected in the probability value and t-value of the study.
- The researchers recommended that students under the controlled group can also use Jamboard at its optimum level in order for them to also develop and enhance their writing competency.
- The researchers recommended that English instructors should utilize Jamboard in developing the writing competency of the learners, not only limited and confined in Stylistics and Discourse Analysis but also

to other courses which require the enhancement of writing skills and competency.

- The researchers also recommended that future researchers should conduct a mixed-method research study relative to Jamboard as an interactive platform toward students' writing competency in order to broaden the scope of knowledge, understanding and findings. The mixed-method study will also allow researchers to add supporting evidences and information based on the experiences of the respondents in the intervention.

D. REFLECTION

One of the strengths of an English major students is the ability to write comprehensively, competently and meaningfully. Having said this, writing competency should be developed, taught and hone with the most appropriate and innovative way, platform and pedagogy.

Through the course of the study, it is deemed that even English major students still need reinforcement and enhancement in terms of their writing competency. In congruence to this, the findings of this research study revealed that the Jamboard as an interactive platform is helpful and effective toward the writing competency of the students. This is reflected in the significant difference results and probability value that there is a significant difference in the posttest mean scores between controlled and treatment group which proves the effectiveness of Jamboard to the writing competency of the respondents under treatment or intervention group.

All in all, the researchers realized that even writing skill and competency is a difficult skill to develop, technological platform and pedagogy such as Jamboard can aid the enhancement, improvement and development of writing competency. Therefore, Jamboard is viewed and utilized in an advantageous optic.

VI. ACTION PLAN/ PLANS FOR DISSEMINATION AND UTILIZATION

The faculty of the College of Education in Don Honorio Ventura State University, specifically the English instructors, most especially the stylistics teacher, will be informed about the findings of the study regarding the utilization of Jamboard as interactive platform toward the writing competency of the learners particularly the 3rd year English major students who are taking Stylistics and Discourse Analysis course. As the administration of College of Education considered the findings and effectiveness of the intervention, a proposal and action plan will be crafted in order for the English teachers to maximize the usage of technology while targeting the macro skills such as writing skills of the learners. Lastly, an evaluation and observation of the College Dean to the English instructors will also be proposed and recommended in order to monitor the quality education and the utilization of intervention.

Hence, the action plan is reflected below.

Implementation Steps (What will be Done?)	Responsibilities (Who will do?)	Resources (Funding/ Time/ People /Materials)	Timeline (By when? /Day /Month)
I. Submit the results (Action research) to the experiential learning coordinator.	Researcher	Experiential Learning Coordinator	May 27, 2022
II. Show the outcome and intervention to dean, stylistic teacher and other English instructors	Researcher	Dean of the College of Education, stylistic teachers and English Instructors	June 2022
III. Use the findings in addressing the problems of English major students in terms of writing competency in other English-related subjects/courses.	Researcher	English major students and English instructors	July to December 2022
IV. Conduct action research with similar intervention to address a specific problem.	Researcher	Future Researchers	January 2023

Table 8: ACTION PLAN

Goal: To determine and evaluate the effectiveness of Google Jamboard as an interactive platform toward students' writing competency in Stylistics and Discourse Analysis.

Program Objective: To recommend actions to implement Jamboard as an interactive platform toward enhancing and developing the writing competency of the English major students.

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